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14. Effect of Bruner's Concept Attainment Model on Retention of Concepts in Punjabi in Relation to Cognitive Styles
by *Dr. Parvinder K. Kamboj* 121-128
15. Right to Education Act-2009: Gaps, Challenges and Remedies
By *Dr. Jagdish Chander Mehta* 129-139
16. Future of Education in India
By *Dr. Ram Mehar and Dr. Supreet Kaur* 140-145
17. Soft Skills of Children in Relation to Their Fluid Intelligence
By *Dr. Bimla Dhanda and Dr. Chandra Kala Singh* 146-149
18. Impact of Intervention Programme on Visual-Motor Integration Skills of Slow Learner Children
By *Dr. Sheela Sangwan and Dr. Shanti Balda* 150-155
19. Developmental Outcomes of Disadvantaged Children
By *S. Kaushal and Dr. C.K. Singh* 156-160
20. Changing Parent- Child Relationship
By *Punam Midha* 161-168
21. Organizational Climate of Government and Private Schools in Relation To Leadership Style of the Principals
By *Sumita vig* 169-175
22. Evaluative Study of Mid Day Meal Scheme in Chandigarh.
By *Dr. Kanwalpreet Kaur and Dr. Jatinder Grover* 176-187
- ✓ 23. Spatial Patterns of Disparity in Urban Rural Literacy in Himachal Pradesh.
By *Dr. Rajan Bhandari* 188-198
24. Islam and Islamization in Medieval India: A Study of Communalist Historical Writings.
By *Parampreet Kaur* 199-213
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Spatial Patterns of Disparity in Urban Rural Literacy in Himachal Pradesh.

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ABSTRACT

Himachal Pradesh, being one of the most literate states in the country, does not mean uniformly high level of literacy in the entire state. There are wide differences in literacy rates in urban and rural areas. Differences between rural and urban literacy are basically the outcome of variations in socio-economic and cultural conditions in the two types of areas. The present study seeks to find out the spatial patterns of disparities in literacy in urban rural population in Himachal Pradesh. The difference in percentage points between urban and rural literacy rates can be a deceptive indicator since it is always a small figure regardless of whether the literacy rates is very low or very high. Disparity index is a more sophisticated measure. Disparity index has been worked out on the basis of the formula suggested by Kundu and Rao, (1986) the suggested formula is in fact a modified version of Sopher's Index (1974) for measurement of disparity.

$$DS = \log (X2/X1) + \log (200-X1)/(200-X2),$$

DS= Disparity Index

X2 > = X1; X2 and X1 are the literacy rates of the two groups between which disparity is computed. In case of disparity by residence the reference category is males. X2 = Urban

literacy and X1 = Rural literacy. Besides literacy rates, index of education standard has been calculated for understanding level of education at district level. The formula used in the present study is given below.

$$IOES = \frac{\sum I. E. Y.}{7 + Population} \times \frac{Literate Population}{Illiterate Population}$$

IOES = Index of Education Standard; $\sum I. E. Y.$ = Summation of Integrated Education Years; 7+ population = Population which is more than 7 years old; Literate Population =

Total number of literates above 7 years of age in the total population and; Illiterate population = Total number of illiterates excluding children below 7 years of age in the total population. The index of education standard has been calculated by giving weight to different education standards and then multiplying the minimum number of years required to complete the respective education with the number of literates (Bhandari, 2010).

Introduction:

The disparities in urban and rural areas are associated with a variety of socio-economic factors. The socio-economic conditions in urban areas require educated residents who consequently generate more facilities for education in urban areas than rural areas. The differences are essentially a function of socio-cultural and economic diversity between two areas (Sagar, 1990, p 75). Cultural differences between the urban areas and the countryside are the product of

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sharp resistance from the native culture of rural areas to the alien culture of urban areas and the social change can take place only by enhancing the interaction between them (Hoselitz, 1960, p 148). Moreover, urban areas, where literacy rates are high also diffuse education to rural areas, depending upon the size of urban centre and its connectivity with rural areas. The diffusion of literacy from urban areas depends upon the degree of interaction, the adaptive behavior, the favorable outlook and the progressive attitude of rural population towards education (Sagar, 1990, p 75).

Rural and urban areas, particularly in developing countries, present contrast with regard to overall setup. Good road network, provision of large social infrastructure and job opportunities make urban areas different from rural areas. Urban population tends to recognize the importance of literacy and education and generates resources to attain a higher level in this field.

Literacy is a direct outcome of standard of education prevailing in different districts. Sharp differences exist between rural and urban areas. Table 2 clearly reveals the difference between education standard between rural and urban population. In Himachal Pradesh, one-fourth of the total numbers of literates in the rural areas of the whole state have received education up to the primary level. In sharp contrast with this, in urban population of the state only a little less than one-fourth of the total number of literates have studied up to the matriculation level. Again, graduates constitute 18.22 percent of the total urban population whereas no more than 3.77 percent of the rural population of the state is graduate. Value of index of education standard in Rural Himachal was 9.40 as compared to urban index value of 31.80. Chamba district had the lowest index value of 3.63 and Hamirpur registered 15.27 in rural population. In case of urban population, Una district had the lowest value and Shimla district registered the highest value (Table 1).

The difference in literacy levels between urban and rural areas is the result of magnitude and pattern of diffusion of literacy from urban to rural areas and the provision of educational facilities in rural areas. In case of Himachal Pradesh big towns have worked as centers of diffusion of literacy for rural areas. Small towns however played a relatively less important role in this regard. Moreover rural literacy is also determined by the magnitude of out-migration of literate rural population to urban centers and thus lowering the rural literacy rate. A high degree of diffusion of literacy toward rural areas; and a low rate of rural to urban migration of educated persons are important contributory factors to ensure low urban-rural difference in literacy. Contrarily, if an urban center (for example, an industrial town) does not work as a center of literacy diffusion to the adjoining rural areas and educated population from the urban center moves towards other urban centers, it would result in high disparity between urban and rural levels of literacy.

Disparities in urban-rural literacy

As per 2001 Census, Himachal Pradesh was a predominantly rural state with only small patches of urbanized areas. Out of a total number of 109 tehsils in all the 12 districts of the state,

only 42 tehsils in 10 districts had urban settlement(s) in some areas. Shimla Urban was the only tehsil in the whole state that was entirely urban. In the succeeding sections the status of urban-rural disparity is examined in 41 tehsils of the state that have both rural and urban segments of population. According to 2001 census with 76.48 percent overall literacy rate the state had a difference of 13.87 percent points between rural (75.08 percent) and urban (88.95 percent) areas. Among the districts, Una registered lowest (1.95 percent points) and Chamba (28.96 percent points) was at the top in urban-rural difference in literacy. Among tehsils Chamba registered the highest (29.31 percent points). At the lowest extreme was Palampur with a negative urban rural difference of -2.84 percent points in literacy, as rural literacy (80.93 percent) was found to be more than urban literacy (78.09 percent).

Table: 1

Himachal Pradesh: Rural Urban Disparity in Literacy, 2001

District	Total Literacy	Urban Literacy	Rural Literacy	Disparity Index	Urban-Rural Difference
Himachal Pr.	76.48	88.95	75.08	0.1247	13.87
Chamba	62.91	89.50	60.63	0.2699	28.86
Kangra	80.08	86.62	79.70	0.0619	6.92
Lahul & Spiti	73.10	N.U.	73.10	N.U.	N.U.
Kullu	72.90	87.99	71.55	0.1493	16.44
Mandi	75.24	90.51	74.08	0.1477	16.43
Hamirpur	82.46	89.34	81.90	0.0660	7.43
Una	80.37	82.14	80.19	0.0175	1.95
Bilaspur	77.76	89.08	76.97	0.1085	12.11
Solan	76.57	87.97	73.94	0.1267	14.03
Sirmaur	70.39	87.80	68.29	0.1787	19.50
Shimla	79.12	91.75	75.19	0.1483	16.56
Kinnaur	75.20	N.U.	75.20	N.U.	N.U.

Source: Calculated from census of India 2001

Keeping in mind the urban-rural literacy disparity negative index in Palampur (-0.026), and the highest in Chamba tehsil (0.273) and the state average (0.125), three categories of urban-rural disparity index have been demarcated.

1. Areas with high disparity index in urban-rural literacy rates, where index value is more than 0.140
2. Areas with low disparity index in urban-rural literacy, where index value is less than 0.070
3. Areas with moderate disparity index in urban-rural literacy, where index value is between 0.071 and 0.140

If the state is divided across the north-south line all areas with low disparity in urban rural literacy are located in the western part and most of the areas with moderate disparity index are in the eastern part of the divide. Areas with a high disparity index are more or less following the

Table: 2
Himachal Pradesh: Standard of Education in Rural and Urban Areas, 2001

State/ District	Percent Literate as Percent to Total Literates																	
	Literate without education		Below Primary		Primary		Middle		Matric/Secondary		Higher secondary/Intermediate		Tech/Non tech diploma or certificate		Graduate & above		Index of Education Standard	
	R	U	R	U	R	U	R	U	R	U	R	U	R	U	R	U	R	U
Himachal Pradesh	1.54	0.96	21.27	12.24	28.87	16.88	17.48	14.17	19.66	23.49	6.67	12.27	0.73	1.74	3.77	18.22	9.40	31.38
Chamba	1.87	0.95	31.09	15.12	32.04	19.25	13.79	14.85	13.88	23.11	4.35	11.28	0.64	1.32	2.33	14.10	3.63	30.12
Kangra	1.17	1.29	17.63	13.77	28.12	19.11	18.80	14.29	21.65	22.64	7.67	12.11	0.84	1.55	4.11	15.22	13.08	25.84
Lahul & S.	6.17	0.00	24.44	0.00	25.17	0.00	15.22	0.00	16.27	0.00	6.02	0	1.31	0.00	5.39	0.00	8.66	N.U.
Kullu	1.62	1.09	28.94	13.39	30.01	17.29	15.12	13.95	14.54	23.44	5.68	13.29	0.46	1.41	3.62	16.11	6.90	28.74
Mandi	1.38	0.96	21.11	11.19	29.27	15.42	16.58	12.68	20.77	23.95	6.74	14.12	0.83	3.47	3.29	18.16	8.87	37.38
Hamirpur	0.84	0.92	15.28	11.76	27.29	18.29	20.26	15.22	22.89	22.74	8.38	11.79	0.72	3.12	4.34	16.11	15.27	31.45
Una	1.11	0.78	18.18	14.49	28.92	21.21	18.70	15.87	21.92	23.79	6.54	9.86	0.99	2.13	3.62	11.86	12.72	17.43
Bilaspur	1.35	1.04	17.07	12.63	30.13	17.26	18.58	14.61	20.50	22.55	7.51	13.36	0.69	2.19	4.15	16.33	11.08	29.85
Solan	1.44	0.86	21.04	10.97	29.52	16.15	18.03	16.49	18.83	25.23	6.27	11.21	0.76	1.97	4.09	17.11	8.72	28.95
Sirmaur	2.10	0.98	31.00	12.89	31.78	18.50	15.14	14.07	12.97	21.45	4.02	12.18	0.50	1.28	2.48	18.61	5.31	26.72
Shimla	2.84	0.90	22.26	11.30	25.81	14.73	16.75	12.81	20.74	23.59	6.61	12.68	0.45	0.95	4.52	23.00	9.72	42.41
Kinnaur	1.49	0.00	25.86	0.00	28.79	0.00	17.64	0.00	15.47	0.00	5.76	0	0.99	0.00	3.99	0.00	9.40	N.U.

Source: Calculated from Census of India 2001. N.U. -No Urban Population

National Highway 21 (N.H. 21).

1. Areas with high disparity index in urban-rural literacy rates

Out of a total of 41 tehsils as mentioned above there were 15 tehsils where disparity index in urban-rural literacy was more than 0.140. Chamba, Kullu, and Shimla districts had three in each; Bilaspur, Mandi Sirmour districts had two in each; and Solan district with one tehsil displayed high disparity index i.e. more than 0.140. Mandi and Chamba tehsils with district headquarters had lowest and highest disparity index respectively in this category.

There were three distinct pockets in the state with high disparity index of more than 0.140. Firstly, in the north-western part of the state in Chamba district; Dalhousie (0.162), Bhattiyat (0.224) and Chamba tehsils (0.273) formed a small pocket of high disparity index. Secondly in the southern part of the state, Nahan (0.145) and Paonta Sahib tehsils (0.169) formed another small pocket. Besides these two pockets the third pocket formed an inverted U shape comprising Nalagarh (0.168), Naina Devi (0.169), Bilaspur (0.147), Sundar Nagar (0.143), Mandi (0.142), Kullu (0.157), Banjar (0.199), Rampur (0.152), Rohru (0.149) and Jubbal tehsils (0.158).

The first pocket, as mentioned above, covered southern part of Chamba district. Chamba tehsil displayed highest urban-rural disparity index (0.273) in the state. Chamba town registered a high literacy of 90.15 percent. The surrounding rural areas were marked by a low rural literacy of 60.84 percent and thus resulted in high urban rural disparity of 0.273. Taking the district as a whole, Chamba district had a high proportion of scheduled castes and scheduled tribes in rural areas. In fact, Chamba district had the highest number of Gaddis and Gujjars in the state. These tribes practiced transhumance and migrated season-wise. The literacy level among these tribes was very low and contributed to overall lowering of rural literacy rates. In recent past, rural population had to travel large distances to acquire education. This indicates that majority could not attend schools during severe winters. The distance from home to school played more crucial role in case of female literacy because there prevailed a taboo against sending a female child outside the village for education. All these factors had contributed to low literacy rates in rural areas, thus widening the urban-rural gap.

The second pocket covering Paonta Sahib and Nahan town also displayed high urban-rural disparity. Nahan displayed urban-rural disparity index of 0.145, and Paonta Sahib was marked with 0.169. Nahan and Paonta Sahib both had urban literacy of more than 85 percent; and low rural literacy level of 72.82 percent and 67.97 percent respectively. The two towns of Nahan and Paonta Sahib were large in size and functioned as central places for their respective tehsils but could not diffuse literacy to rural areas. Moreover educated persons from rural as well as urban areas were largely attracted by big cities like Dehradun and Chandigarh for education purposes.

The third pocket shaped as an inverted 'U' formed another area with high urban rural disparity. This pocket covered four sets which recorded high urban rural disparity. Firstly with important urban centers like Bhuntar (an important air port of the state encouraging tourism

industry) and Kullu (a district head quarter as a nodal point for tourists and tourism trade route linking Punjab with Leh), urban literacy was high and rural literacy was low because of a large proportion of scheduled caste population.

Secondly, Rampur and Rohru, class V towns, and Banjar and Jubbal class VI towns registered high urban literacy but low literacy rate was displayed by the rural areas of Rampur, Rohru, Banjar and Jubbal tehsils. The low rural literacy level was attributed to abysmally low female literacy i.e. 64.12 percent, 57.36 percent, 59.46 percent, 56.73 percent in Rampur, Rohru, Jubbal and Banjar tehsils as compared to corresponding figures of 85.94 percent, 85.54 percent, 83.85 percent, and 84.15 respectively for rural male population.

The third set in the inverted 'U', as mentioned above, is formed by tehsils of Mandi and Sundernagar and Bilaspur including Class III towns of Mandi and Sundernagar and Class IV town of Bilaspur and their rural areas. Mandi and Bilaspur towns were district headquarters to their respective districts. No doubt, these towns were large in size, accommodated a number of district administrative offices, offered employment to large number of persons and also diffused literacy to rural areas, but, educated villagers opted for migration to urban centers or big cities in the state or the adjoining states. All these three towns with high urban literacy are located at N.H. 21 and continued to receive large development projects as compared to rural areas. The urban literacy rate in Bilaspur, Mandi and Sundernagar tehsils was relatively high i.e. 91.46 percent, 92.24 percent and 89.67 percent respectively. The rural literacy rates for the respective centers were 75.06 percent (Bilaspur), 76.37 percent (Mandi) and 73.74 percent (Sundamagar). This widened the urban rural gap in literacy rates.

The last link in the inverted 'U' is formed by rural and urban areas of Nalagarh and Naina Devi. Nalagarh tehsil included two urban centers of Baddi and Nalagarh town which are coming up as important industrial towns of the state but their presence is unable to change rapidly the economic and social setup in rural areas.

Similarly Naina Devi tehsil with high urban literacy (90.33 percent) and low rural literacy (71.63 percent) widened the urban rural gap in literacy. Naina Devi, a small religious town, could not diffuse literacy to rural areas and had a little impact on rural areas in terms of literacy. Moreover, in Naina Devi tehsil there was 27.78 percent scheduled caste population and 13.07 percent scheduled tribe population in rural population. These segments of population were mostly engaged in primary activities such as cattle rearing which lowered rural literacy and widened the gap.

Thus, areas experiencing high disparity in urban rural literacy were associated with tehsils showing high urban literacy and low rural literacy rates. High urban literacy was associated with status of district headquarter of town and other urban centres. Low rural literacy was because of high proportion of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population in rural areas; agricultural base of rural society and low female literacy. Low diffusion of literacy campaigns from urban to rural areas and out migration of educated and economically well off people from rural to urban areas thus resulted in high disparity index in urban-rural literacy.

2. *Areas with low disparity index in urban-rural literacy rates*

Keeping in mind the state average of 0.125 and large variations, the areas which experienced a disparity index of less than 0.070 in urban rural literacy have been considered in the category of low disparity index. Areas with low disparity index in urban rural literacy experienced low and also negative index of disparity in one special case of Palampur tehsil. In all, 13 tehsils with a low disparity index in urban-rural literacy, ranging from -0.026 in Palampur tehsil to 0.069 in Barsar tehsil belonged to this category.

It is important to mention here that Palampur tehsil in Kangra district is the only tehsil in the state of Himachal Pradesh which registered a negative disparity index (-0.026) in urban-rural literacy. In other words in Palampur, rural literacy rate (80.93 percent) was higher than urban literacy rate (78.09 percent). Palampur tehsil was at 15th position in terms of rural literacy and was at the bottom in case of urban literacy among all tehsils in the state. It was due to higher literacy rate among rural population than urban population. It was so because of the location of Agriculture University, Palampur in the countryside of the tehsil. Moreover many well educated families of the town living in the rural areas further raised the proportion of literates in the rural areas.

Broadly speaking, areas with low disparity index in urban rural literacy rates in Himachal Pradesh included (i) large parts of Kangra district Dera Gopipur (0.051), Dharamshala (0.062) Nurpur (0.065) and Palampur tehsil (-0.026); (ii) Hamirpur (0.055), Nadaun (0.062) and Barsar tehsils (0.069) in Hamirpur district; (iii) Una (0.009) and Amb tehsils (0.057) in Una district; (iv) Ghumarwin (0.049) and Jhanduta (0.053) in Bilaspur district; (v) Sarkaghat tehsil (0.060) Manali (0.045) and Kasauli tehsils (0.050) in Mandi, Kullu and Solan district respectively.

As far as other large parts of Kangra including tehsils of Dera Gopipur (0.051), Dharamshala (0.062) and Nurpur (0.065) are concerned, these were marked by low index of urban-rural disparity which was the result of high rural literacy and moderate urban literacy (Map1). Increased pressure on land and low agricultural output made villagers look for employment in tertiary sector requiring literacy and education.

The second pocket of Hamirpur (0.055), Nadaun (0.062) and Barsar tehsils (0.069) in Hamirpur district also recorded low index of urban-rural disparity due to high rural literacy because of diversified non-agricultural occupational structure and moderate urban literacy.

The third pocket of low disparity index was formed by Una and Amb tehsils in Una district. These were parts of erstwhile Punjab State and well connected with neighboring region. High rural literacy (79.69 percent) in Una is slightly less than urban literacy (80.64 percent) because of high rural urban interaction

The fourth pocket of Ghumarwin (0.049) and Jhanduta (0.053) in Bilaspur district formed another pocket of low disparity index in urban rural literacy. These tehsils recorded low urban literacy and low rural literacy and thus low index of urban rural disparity.

The fifth region covering the scattered tehsils of Sarkaghat (0.060) Manali (0.045) and Kasauli (0.050) in the districts of Mandi, Kullu and Solan respectively also recorded low index of urban-rural disparity in literacy. Manali a favorite tourist destination has influenced socio-economic conditions in the town. Many educated persons of Lahul-spiti and Kullu have also migrated to countryside of Manali. Relatively high rural literacy rate thus helped in reducing the urban-rural disparity.

Kasauli tehsil in Solan district has two urban centers i.e. Kasauli a cantonment town, set up by the Britishers and Parwanoo, a small recently emerging industrial town. Kasauli town had a literacy rate of 88.96 percent and Parwanoo had 81.95 percent. Parwanoo being an industrial town had relatively low literacy. Both towns represented an urban literacy rate of 84.56 percent as compared to rural literacy rate of 79.02 percent of the Kasauli tehsil. The rural urban gap was less due to low urban literacy and reasonably high rural literacy.

Thus, tehsils with narrow urban rural gap were those where moderate or low urban literacy and high rural literacy rates were found. The overall literacy level in these tehsils was also found to be high. These areas were well connected to neighboring areas and the rural population was well exposed to the external influences. The habitations of well off families in rural areas rather than in congested urban areas also resulted in high rural literacy. The diffusion of literacy from urban to rural areas thus reduced urban-rural disparity in literacy.

3. Areas with moderate disparity index in urban-rural literacy rates

In all there were 12 tehsils which recorded an urban rural disparity index of more than 0.071 and less than 0.140 in urban-rural literacy rates. Most of these tehsils constituted a continuous pocket in the south-eastern part of the state including large parts of Shimla, Sirmaur and Solan districts (Map 1). Rajgarh tehsil (0.079), in Sirmaur district; Solan (0.100) and Arki tehsils (0.105) in Solan district; and Kotkhai (0.136), Chaupal (0.108), Seoni (0.102), Theog (0.100), Kumharsain (0.097) and Shimla Rural tehsils (0.090) were in the category of moderate disparity index.

In addition to the tehsils mentioned above, areas contiguous to them viz. Kangra, Tira Sujanpur and Jogindernagar also displayed moderate disparity index. Kangra, Tira Sujanpur had slightly high level of rural literacy as well as urban literacy whereas Joginder Nagar displayed slightly low literacy both in rural and urban population. Generally speaking the tehsils which had literacy slightly higher or lower than the state average displayed moderate disparity index in urban-rural literacy.

Tehsils with moderate index of disparity in urban rural literacy rates were those which displayed high literacy in rural areas and moderate to high literacy in urban areas. These areas had good rural economy characterised by horticulture, particularly in tehsils of Shimla district. These areas were also associated with development in transport network and diversification of economy.

Conclusion

Despite the 5th position among all states of the nation, there persisted large disparities in urban rural literacy rates in Himachal Pradesh. As per 2001 census, 75.08 percent of the rural population was literate as against the 88.95 percent of urban population, implying a difference of 13.87 percent points and a disparity index of 0.124. The disparity in urban and rural literacy rates was found to be broadly attributable to the differences in the functional needs of education, facilities made available for education, level of urban-rural interaction and out migration of rural literate.

In Himachal Pradesh areas with low disparity in urban rural literacy rate were located in the western part and the most of the areas with moderate disparity index were in the eastern part of the state. Areas with higher disparity index in urban rural literacy were more or less concentrated along the National Highway 21.

Areas experiencing high disparity in urban rural literacy rates were associated with tehsils with district headquarters displaying high literacy and large volume of rural to urban migration of literate population and thus leaving rural areas with low literacy rates and consequently further lowering the already low literacy rate of the rural area. A high proportion of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population in the total population of the rural areas, the agricultural base of rural society and low female literacy contributed as the main factors for keeping low level of literacy in rural areas. Low diffusion of literacy from urban to rural areas and high magnitude of rural to urban migration of the educated class as well as economically well off people resulted in high disparity index in urban rural literacy rates.

Areas with small urban rural disparity were those which had low to moderate urban literacy and reasonably high rural literacy. These areas were well connected to surrounding areas and the rural population was well exposed to outside influences.

Areas with moderate urban rural literacy disparity were those which displayed high literacy in rural areas and moderate to high literacy in urban areas. These areas had good prosperous rural economy characterised by horticultural development, particularly in the tehsils of Shimla district. These areas were associated with developed transport network and diversified economy.

References:

- Bhandari, R. (2010) Spatial Temporal and Social Variations in Literacy in Himachal Pradesh: 1971-2001, An Unpublished Ph. D. Thesis, Department of Geography, Panjab University, Chandigarh pp 118-43.
- Census of Himachal Pradesh (2001) Primary Census Abstract, Director of Census Operation Himachal Pradesh, Shimla.
- Census of India (2001) Himachal Pradesh, Provisional Population Totals, Paper – 2 of 2001, Director of Census Operation, Himachal Pradesh.
- Census of India (2001) Population Profiles (India, State and Union Territory), Registrar general India New Delhi.
- Hoselitz, B. F. (1960) "The Urban-Rural Contrast as a Factor in Social Change", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Annual, pp. 145-152.
- Human Development Report Himachal Pradesh (2002) Planning Commission, New Delhi.
- Krishan, G. and Shyam, M. (1974) "Literacy Pattern in Indian Cities", *Geoform*, Vol. 19, pp. 77-80.
- Krishan, G. and Shyam, M. (1978) "Regional Aspects of Urban and Rural Differential in Literacy in India 1971", *The Journal of Developing Areas*, Vol. 13, No. 1, October, pp. 11-21.
- Kundu, A. and Rao (1986) "Inequity in Educational Development: Issues in Measurement, Changing Structure and its Socio-Economic Correlated with Special Reference to India", in Moonis Raza (Ed.) 'Educational Planning: A Long Term Perspective', New Delhi: NIEPA and Concept Publishing Company.
- Raju, S. (1988) "Female Literacy in India: The Urban Dimension", *Economic and Political Weekly*, 23(44).
- Sagar P. (1990) Spatial Patterns of Literacy Differentials in India: 1981, Thesis submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in the Faculty of Arts Panjab University Chandigarh, India.
- Sopher, D. E. (1980) "Sex Disparity in Indian Literacy", in An Exploration of India: Geographical Perspectives on Society and Culture, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, pp. 130-187.